

Microcanonical Distribution, Equally Weighted Microstates, Entropy and Virtual Work

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The microcanonical distribution for a classical gas involves a fixed number of particles N and a fixed total energy E . The energy may be distributed in different ways among the N particles such that its total is E and each distribution or microstate is said to have the same weight or probability. We argue that the idea of equal weight follows directly from Newtonian mechanics. For a dense gas, the collisions in the gas are Newtonian and if there were a greater weight to have e_1, e_1, e_1 (for three particles) than $3e_1, 0, 0$, there would need to be a reason for this coming from Newtonian physics. In other words, this is not a statistical issue. Equal distribution of energy among particles has important consequences because one may immediately write $P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_i+e_j)$, if one relaxes the total energy constraint (canonical distribution). This leads directly to $P(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. The underlying idea, however, is present in the microcanonical distribution. The idea that energy distributions carry the same weight also leads to the notion of the maximization of the number of distributions or the maximization of entropy for the gas. Thus we argue that maximization of entropy subject to a constraint on total average energy is not an independent statistical idea, at least for the usual classical gas, but follows from Newtonian mechanics.

In (1), it is argued that the equal weights for microstates in a microcanonical gas follow from the notion of virtual work being zero. We argue that the equal weights follow from Newtonian mechanics which does not show any preference for e_1, e_1, e_1 versus $3e_1, 0, 0$ for three particles.

Microcanonical Distribution and Information

Given a classical gas with N particles and a fixed total energy of E , one may imagine distributing this energy to the N particles in many different ways. In a microcanonical distribution, these microstates or distributions are given a priori equal weights. We ask: Could the weights be different without Newtonian mechanics indicating the reason? We argue that Newtonian mechanics allows for all different possible collisions and energy distributions and so if some were weighted differently than others, there would need to be a physical reason for this. These arguments could be made using a few particles to show that say e_1, e_1, e_1 does not have the same probability as $3e_1, 0, 0$ for three particles. Thus we argue that the equal weight argument is Newtonian.

The consequences of the equal weight argument in a microcanonical ensemble are important. We argue that two ideas follow:

- (A) $P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_i+e_j)$ if one relaxes the total fixed energy constraint, one has: $P(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ where T is temperature. This is called the canonical distribution.
- (B) The idea of all distributions carrying the same weight means one wishes to compute all possible energy distributions. Relaxing the constraint of a total fixed energy and replacing it with $E_{\text{average}} = \text{constant} = \sum_i p(e_i) e_i$, one has $N p(e_i)$ particles in each state e_i . One may calculate the number of arrangements using $N! / \text{Product over } i$

$n(e_i)!$. This number should be maximized subject to $E_{\text{average}} = \text{constant}$ because all distributions are allowed. This leads to the idea of the maximization of entropy (Shannon's entropy in this case) which yields the same result as $P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_i+e_j)$.

Thus we argue that what looks like two statistical ideas, (A) and (B), are really the consequence of Newtonian mechanics carried over into a picture of a relaxed average energy.

Virtual Work

In (1), it is argued that the equal probabilities of each microstate in the microcanonical distribution follow directly from the notion of virtual work being zero. Virtual work is a concept in classical mechanics. We argue that classical mechanics already indicates each microstate has the same probability a priori because there are not mechanical arguments preferring one distribution over the other.

Virtual work is defined in (1) as :

$$dW = \text{Sum over } i=1, N \quad d e_{ki} + d e_{pi} \quad ((1))$$

There are N particles and $d e_{ki}$ is the kinetic energy of particle i and $d e_{pi}$ the potential. Next, this idea is applied to a statistical system which may have different microstates of N particles, each with a probability p_j and an energy E_j . (1) states:

$$dW = \text{Sum over } j=1, w \quad p_j dE_j \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{Next: } d \text{ Sum over } j \quad p_j E_j = d(E_{\text{ave}}) = dW + \text{Sum over } j \quad E_j dp_j \quad ((3))$$

It is then argued that for a microcanonical gas, $dE_{\text{ave}}=0$ and $dW=0$ (virtual work) so

$$\text{Sum over } j \quad E_j dp_j = 0 \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is modified to include the constraint: $\text{Sum over } j \quad dp_j = 0$ ((5)) i.e.

$$\text{Sum over } j \quad E_j dp_j + \text{Sum over } j \quad dp_j = 0 \quad ((6))$$

It is then argued that $p_j = 1/w$ where $j=1, w$ i.e. p_j is a constant for each microstate in the microcanonical ensemble and that this result follows directly from virtual work being 0. We agree that the idea of equal weights follows from classical mechanics, but argue that if p_j represents the probability of a state in a microcanonical distribution, then $E_j=E$ for all j . If that is the case: $\text{Sum over } j \quad dp_j=0$, but this is a given and does not prove that $p_j=1/w$. We argue that $p_j=1/w$ follows from the idea that Newtonian mechanics does not give any reason for different probabilities for distributing energy, i.e. $3e_1, 0, 0$ and e_1, e_1, e_1 have the same weight for three particles.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the idea that all microstates in a microcanonical distribution have the same weight follows from Newtonian mechanics. If there were different weights, there would need to be a classical mechanical reason for it. Thus, e_1, e_1, e_1 and $3e_1, 0, 0$ for three particles should have the same probability. This is equivalent to the idea $P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_i + e_j)$ which holds fully in a system in which one relaxes the total E constraint, i.e. the canonical distribution. In fact, using this relation, one finds: $P(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. This same relaxation of the total energy constraint may be used together with the idea of equal weights to develop the idea of maximum entropy. In such a case: $E_{ave} = \text{constant} = \sum_i e_i n(e_i)$ where $n(e_i) = N p(e_i)$. One may calculate the number of arrangements, take \ln , use Stirling's approximation and maximize (because one wants to include all possible distributions) subject to $E_{ave} = \text{constant}$. This is the maximization of energy approach which is the same as $P(e_i)P(e_i) = P(e_i + e_j)$. Both of these follow from the equal microstate weight of a microcanonical distribution and this follows, in turn, from Newtonian mechanics, we argue.

In (1) it is argued that equal weights of microcanonical microstates follow from the notion of virtual work, but we argue that this is present a priori from Newtonian mechanics which allows all energy distributions with equal weights, without favouring one over the other.

References

1. Wang, Q. Seeing maximum entropy from the principle of virtual work (2006 or later)
<https://arxiv.org/vc/arxiv/papers/0704/0704.1076v4.pdf>